

COURT COSTS IN CIVIL PROCEEDINGS

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Abstract: This article describes the concept and types of court costs in civil proceedings, expenses related to proceedings and the role of court costs in foreign legislation.

Key words: Court costs, state duty, types of state duty, ordinary state duty, proportional state duty, expenses related to the consideration of the case.

Chapter 13 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is called "Court costs", and in this chapter, the concept of court costs and the rules for their collection are defined.[1]

The guarantee that every person will protect his conflicting rights or interests through the court is guaranteed on the basis of the constitution and legal documents. The procedure for applying to civil courts and the requirements for such an application are regulated by the Code of Civil Procedure and other legal documents. Court expenses are the expenses stipulated by the law incurred by the persons participating in the case related to the hearing and settlement of the civil case. [2]

The introduction of court costs has a number of purposes. Although the funds received as a result of the state tax are not very important, they are focused on covering the expenses in the process of continuing the court's activities.

The civil procedural legislation of our country envisages the following two types of court costs:

- state tax
- expenses related to handling the case.[3]

The state duty charged for civil cases is the sum of money charged to the state revenue for considering and deciding a civil case. State duty is a mandatory fee charged for the performance of legally significant actions and the issuance of documents by authorized institutions and officials for such actions.[4]

According to paragraph 3 of the decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 14 of November 24, 2009 "On the practice of collecting court costs in civil cases", the state duty in civil cases is charged from the following :

- 1) from lawsuits submitted to courts, from applications for cases conducted in a separate procedure;

- 2) from applications for disputes regarding decisions of the arbitration court;
- 3) applications to issue a writ of execution for compulsory execution of decisions of the arbitration court;
- 4) applications for recognition and enforcement of a decision of a foreign court and a foreign arbitration court (arbitration);

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- 5) appeal, cassation complaints.[5]

In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Duty", state duty, unless otherwise specified in this Law, shall be levied until the legally significant actions for which the state duty is levied are carried out and documents are issued by the authorized institutions. is paid in cash or non-cash.

The state tax is transferred to the State budget based on payment documents, except for the part of the state tax that is left at the disposal of that state body for the services of which state bodies are charged.[4]

State duty can be divided into types depending on the payment procedure:

Ordinary state duty is charged at a fixed, predetermined rate. Currently, the amount of ordinary state duty is related to the amount of basic calculation;

Proportionate state duty is charged as a percentage of the cost of treatment.[6]

Expenses related to the handling of the case include postal expenses related to sending court documents, expenses related to conducting a court hearing in the video conference mode, conducting an examination appointed by an economic court, summoning a witness, taking evidence on the spot. and other expenses to be paid for inspection.

Amounts to be paid to witnesses, experts and specialists, interpreters or amounts necessary for the costs of on-site inspection shall be deposited in the deposit account of the court in advance by the party who made the appropriate request. If this request is submitted by both parties, or if summoning of witnesses, experts, experts, translators, and on-the-spot inspection is carried out at the initiative of the court, the required amount shall be paid by the parties in equal amounts. If the expert is appointed at the initiative of the court, the amount to be paid may be paid to the expert by the court from the deposit account. This amount is collected from the parties involved in the case and transferred to the deposit account of the court when the court document is issued in accordance with the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.[1]

The Civil Procedural Code of the Republic of Ukraine also provides rules on court costs. Basically, Chapter 8 of this Code is called "Legal costs", and Articles 133-142 establish the procedure for collecting court costs. For example, Article 136 of this Code specifies the rules "Delaying and installment payment of court costs, reducing their amount or exempting them from payment" and based on it: taking into account the property situation, by his decision, the court must postpone the payment of the fee for a certain period or pay it in installments, but not later than this period.

In case the court costs are not paid within the time limit set by the court, the application shall be left unconsidered in accordance with Article 257 of this Code, or in cases where the payment of court costs is delayed, the costs shall be collected by the decision of the court. On the grounds provided for in the first part of this article, the court may reduce the amount of court costs to be paid in connection with the consideration of the case or exempt them from payment in accordance with the procedure established by law.

In conclusion, the state tax is a sum of money that must be paid in a fixed amount by law, and the court costs are collected based on the expenses incurred, regardless of the value of the claim. Also, the state tax is charged to the state budget, and the court costs (expenses) are the funds that go to the deposit account of the court and are spent according to the established procedure. Such as partial reimbursement of expenses related to the resolution of disputes related to civil courts from the collection of court costs in civil courts, prevention of cases of unjustified appeals to civil courts, material punishment of the defendant who caused the origin of the dispute or the claimant who appealed to the court without grounds goals are set.

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